

CMIP7 Guidance on Grids

Prepared under oversight by the WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel (WIP)¹

V3.0, 03 June 2026

What grids may be used for reporting CMIP7 variables?

There are few restrictions on the grids used to report CMIP7 model output:

1. Variables may be reported on the model's native grids and/or on grids of a modelling group's choosing, with the awareness that for certain MIP experiments, some variables have been specifically requested to be reported on the native grid.
2. A variable may be reported on multiple grids (e.g., on both a native grid and on some regular latitude by longitude grid preferred by many users). As in CMIP6, providers of high resolution ocean data are encouraged to report the data both at the original resolution and on either a 1x1 degree spherical coordinate grid with one of the cells centred at (0.5 E, 0.5 N) or on a 0.25x0.25 degree spherical coordinate grid with one of the cells centred at (0.125 E, 0.125 N). (These are the grids providing World Ocean Atlas Data.) Similarly, providers of high-resolution atmospheric data are encouraged to report it both at the original resolution and on a 1x1 degree spherical coordinate grid with one of the cells centred at (0.5 E, 0.5 N)
3. Variables representing the same physical quantity but differing by frequency or region can be reported on different grids.
4. For model output, it is recommended that each grid-cell value be representative of the entire grid cell and carried at its cell centre, but it is not forbidden for a variable to represent a value at a cell bound or corner. Analysts usually prefer all variables on a common grid, but there may be some circumstances when reporting variables on different grids could be judged by a modelling group to be of more importance than analysts' preferences.
5. Do not pad a grid with any halo cells at the edges. Do not include, for example, duplicate longitude values at the east or west sides of a latitude-longitude grid.

The [CF conventions](#) describe how to report grids in netCDF files. If a required grid type is not already covered by the CF convention (a novel type of model native grid, for example) then a [CF issue](#) should be opened requesting it be added. A [CMOR issue](#) can be opened if a required grid type covered by the CF conventions is not yet implemented in CMOR. Please note that the

¹ Draft written by K. E. Taylor and subsequently revised with input from J. Anstey, P. J. Durack, D. Hassell, M. Juckes, G. Levasseu, M. Mizielinski, Zebedee Nicholls, M. Schupfner, and M. P. Moine

CMIP7 output requirements document may specify additional requirements or recommendations that extend beyond the CF conventions (e.g., prescribed naming conventions for variables describing cell vertices or bounds). Such requirements are automatically handled by CMOR, while other tools may require explicit implementation.

Are there preferred grids for reporting different variables?

Many modelling groups will choose to report ocean and sea ice variables on one grid and all other variables on a different grid. This is encouraged if by doing so, the fields originally generated by a model are represented with more fidelity. At the same time, when several different variables are needed to address a particular scientific issue, analysts will find it convenient if all those variables are reported on a common grid. When a modelling group chooses to report some variables on an ocean grid and others on an atmospheric grid, it may not always be obvious which variables belong in each category. Here are some general rules to help guide the choice:

1. All variables derived exclusively by the sea ice or ocean model components should be reported on the ocean grid. All other variables should be reported on the atmospheric grid.
2. Variables that characterize conditions at the interface between the atmosphere and ocean (or atmosphere and sea ice) should sometimes be reported on both the atmospheric grid and the ocean grid. If there is a preferred grid, it usually can be determined from the following variable attributes:
 - a. The `standard_name`: If the CF standard name includes “sea” (or “sea ice”), then the variable is meant to characterize the ocean (or “sea ice”) value and be reported on the ocean grid.
 - b. The `cell_methods` attribute: If “where sea”, “where sea ice” or “where ice_free_sea” appears in the `cell_methods`, then the variable should be reported on the ocean grid; otherwise, it should be reported on the atmospheric grid. As an example of a physical parameter requested on two different grids, there are two different requests for `water_evapotranspiration`, one with a `cell_methods` that includes “where ice_free_sea” and the other without a “where” restriction, so it should be reported on both the ocean grid and the atmospheric grid.
 - c. The `cell_measures` attribute: If this attribute is available, the names of area and/or volume variables specified in `cell_measures` may indicate the grid type. For example, “area: areacella” in the CMIP7 Data Request indicates that the atmospheric grid is requested.

How do I obtain unique labels identifying each of my grids?

For each model contributed to CMIP, modelling groups must register the model’s native grids and any non-native grids on which model output is written. Each different grid in CMIP7 will be assigned a unique identifying label that conveys no information on its own (e.g., “g101”, “g134”, “g185”) but will enable users to learn how the grid is defined by consulting the grid register.

The grid properties recorded in the grid register are described in the “[Essential Model Documentation](#)” (EMD). All native grids and output grids (used in reporting regridded data) must be registered prior to writing output files because the assigned grid label is used in constructing the output filenames and directory paths. It will also be recorded as a mandatory global attribute in all files and is generally useful as a short, unique identifier for a grid, Guidance on registering grids is under development in the [EMD GitHub repository](#).

How do I calculate the “nominal_resolution” of a grid?

Before writing CMIP7 data, the “nominal resolution” of the reporting grid must be calculated and recorded as a mandatory global attribute (“nominal_resolution”) in all output files. . The “nominal_resolution” can be calculated for any grid, whether simple (like a regular longitude by latitude grid) or more complex (like a cube-sphere grid or a tri-polar grid). The nominal resolution might be used, for example, to determine what datasets meet the resolution requirements of a given study or to avoid downloading high resolution data that might overwhelm local restrictions on volumes.

The nominal resolution must be calculated following the recipe in [Appendix 2](#) of the [CMIP6 technical specifications document](#). For the common case of a global, regularly spaced lat-lon grid, Appendix 2 provides a formula for calculating nominal resolution. For Gaussian grids, this same formula can be used, substituting the mean latitude spacing for the Gaussian spacing. For equal area grids (HealPIX and other approximately equal-area grids), one need only calculate the maximum width of a single cell, since all cells are similar, and that is the mean resolution. So, for most grids commonly used, the resolution is easy to calculate without the aid of any software.

For grids falling outside those just described, a python code has been written that will calculate nominal_resolution) for any grid. The documentation and links to the code, available on Github, is here: https://pcmdi.github.io/nominal_resolution/html/index.html.